

Computed *F*-ratios were significant at 1% in each case. N, K, and P levels used contributed positively and significantly

to boro rice yield and were ranked first, second, and third, respectively, in importance.

Of the plant nutrients, N and P levels used contributed positively and significantly to aman yield. □

Azolla — a supplemental nitrogen source for flooded rice culture

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In an experiment to evaluate the relative advantage of using *Azolla pinnata* as a supplemental source of nitrogen in combination with fertilizer urea, azolla was added at 5, 10, and 15 t/ha to plots fertilized with urea (see table). The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications at Rajendranagar during 1979-80 kharif. A uniform basal dose of 26 kg P/ha and 30 kg K/ha was applied to all plots. The variety used was Tellahamsa. The nitrogen content of azolla on wet weight basis was 0.25%.

Differences in grain and straw yields were significant among treatments. The

Yield of rice as influenced by azolla and inorganic nitrogen fertilization. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Treatment	Grain		Straw	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield in control	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield in control
100 kg N/ha	3.7	185	4.3	139
87.5 kg N + 5 t azolla/ha	3.6	177	4.1	128
62.5 kg N + 15 t azolla/ha	3.4	162	3.9	117
75 kg N/ha	3.0	131	3.4	89
37.5 kg N + 15 t azolla/ha	3.0	131	3.4	89
50 kg N/ha	2.8	115	3.2	78
25.0 kg N + 10 t azolla/ha	2.7	108	3.1	72
12.5 kg N + 5 t azolla/ha	2.2	69	2.9	61
25 kg N/ha	2.0	54	2.8	56
Control	1.3	—	1.8	—
C.D. at 5%	0.6	—	0.4	—

highest grain yield — 3.7 t/ha — was obtained with 100 kg N/ha supplied through urea. It was significantly higher than that of the other treatments but on par with those obtained with 87.5 kg N + 15 t azolla/ha and 62.5 kg N/ha + 15 t azolla/ha. Similarly the grain yield with 37.5

kg N + 15 t azolla/ha was equal to that with 75 kg N/ha applied through urea. Differences among the other treatments were nonsignificant. In general the grain and straw yields were low because of late planting. □

Azolla as a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice

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A study to assess the potential value of azolla as a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice in sandy soils was made during 1981 kharif in Kerala.

Fourteen treatment groups in a randomized block design with 3 replications included azolla incorporation at 10 t/ha, azolla inoculation at 1 t/ha, a combination of incorporation and inoculation, and a combination of azolla inoculation and nitrogen fertilizer at 30 kg/ha, applied at basal, active tillering, and panicle initiation stages.

Grain yield (2.9 t/ha) and straw yield (3.0 t/ha) were greatest with basal incorporation of azolla combined with dual culturing and in situ incorporation at active tillering stage and 30 kg N/ha applied at panicle initiation. Several other treatments, including a treatment that

Grain and straw yield with azolla incorporation, Kerala, India, 1981.

Treatment ^a			Yield (t/ha)	
Basal	Active tillering	Panicle initiation	Grain	Straw
FN	FN	FN	2.2	2.6
AI	FN	FN	2.6	2.9
FN	AI	FN	2.8	2.9
FN	FN	AI	2.4	2.8
FN+DC	Aii	FN	2.7	2.8
FN+DC	FN	Aii	2.4	2.8
FN+DC	—	FN	2.5	3.0
FN+DC	FN	—	2.3	3.0
FN+DC	—	—	2.4	3.0
AI+DC	FN	—	2.7	3.1
AI+DC	—	FN	2.6	2.9
AI+DC	—	—	2.6	2.8
AI+DC	Aii	FN	2.9	3.0
AI+DC	FN	Aii	2.7	3.1
CD (0.05)			0.38	N.S.

^aFN = 30 kg N/ha, AI = azolla incorporation (10 t/ha), Aii = azolla in situ incorporation (dual culture), DC = dual culture (inoculation @1 t/ha).

received no N fertilizer, had similar yields. The treatment that received 90 kg N/ha in 3 equal splits recorded the lowest grain yield (2.2 t/ha) (see table).

Treatment results indicate azolla is an efficient substitute for N fertilizer in sandy soil where there is likely to be vertical and lateral leaching. This may be because azolla releases N slowly and steadily, thereby limiting N losses. □

Effect of phosphorus fertilizer placement on root and shoot growth of wetland rice

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A pot experiment was conducted to determine the effect of phosphorus (P) placement on root and shoot growth of wetland rice. P was applied to varieties IR42 and MR7 at 0 (surface application), 5, 10, and 15 cm soil depth in 6 replications. Pots were 35 cm in diameter and 45 cm deep. Ten kilograms of clay loam (pH 5.8, organic carbon 1.05%, 0.15% total N, 4 ppm available P, 0.26 meq exchangeable K/100 g, and 17.4 meq CEC/100 g) were added to each pot. Soil was puddled